

Speculation on Quantum Bound Entropy For Crests and Thermodynamics

Francesco R. Ruggeri Hanwell, N.B. June 22, 2022

Shannon's entropy is defined for probabilities as $-\sum_i P(i) \ln(P(i))$. For a probability density, such as spatial or momentum density which appear in quantum bound states i.e. $P(x) = W^*(x)W(x)$ or $P(p) = a(p)^* a(p)$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$, one defines: $S_x = -\int dx P(x) \ln\{P(x)\}$ and $S_p = -\int dp P(p) \ln(P(p))$ (1) and integrates over all space or momentum.

For quantum bound states, however, one may integrate Shannon's entropy using $P(x)$ and/or $P(p)$ only over the region of a single crest. Such a crest is of the form of an unnormalized probability density which has zero probability at the endpoints. Thus the total $P(x)$ and/or $P(p)$ might consist of a set of crests with possibly different heights.

Thus instead of integrating over all x one may consider integrating only over the base of a particular crest to find a local entropy density so to speak. A reason for doing this is that the overall entropy may not satisfy $dE = TdS$, but an entropy for a crest might. We investigate this for an infinite well and an oscillator. For example, for an infinite potential well S_x over the full range 0 to L is independent of n , but by adding energy one creates pockets (crest entropies) which are very low as one has very high resolution. Thus we argue that a quantum bound system has an overall entropy, but also entropies for each crest (whether in x or p space). The latter may be linked to thermodynamics in a different manner than the former.

Infinite Well

The solutions of an infinite well extending from 0 to L are: $C \sin(n\pi x/L)$ with energy $E_n = \frac{\hbar^2 \pi^2 n^2}{2m L^2}$ ((1))

If one calculates $S_x = -\int_{(0,L)} P(x) \ln(P(x)) dx$ it is independent of n . S_p on the other hand is complicated, but depends on n , tending to a constant as n goes to infinite. Thus $dE=TdS$ does not seem to be satisfied if one considers T proportional to energy. $dS_x=0$ and so one would need to have $S=S_x+S_p$ and utilize the dS_p , but it approaches a constant while E_n proportional to n^2 does not.

Consider, however, the notion of spatial entropy of a single crest of $C \sin(n\pi x/L)$. First of all,

$$C^2/p \int_{(0,L)} \sin^2(px) dx = 1 \quad ((2))$$

An integer number of crests n fits within L and each yields the same value for the quantity within $\{ \}$. Thus $C^2 n/p = 1$, but $p=n\pi/L$ so C is independent of n . Thus calculating spatial entropy

$$S_x = -\int_{(0,L)} \frac{1}{p} dx P(x) \ln(P(x)) = \frac{1}{p} n \text{ Constant} \quad ((3))$$

Thus each crest contributes an entropy proportional to $1/n$ i.e. $1/p$.

The energy per crest is: $c_1 n^2/n = c_1 n$ so: $dE(\text{crest}) = c_1 dn$.

dS_x for a crest is $d(c_2 1/n) = -c_2 (1/n^2) dn$. If T is proportional to E i.e. nn then:

TdS_x goes as $c_2 dn$ and the first law of thermodynamics seems to hold. Thus it seems that for fixed L one might apply $dE=TdS$ to a single crest.

What about S_p ? It approaches a constant for large n . If one considers a region of space, then momentum is uncertain for that region and one may consider the fully integrated S_p . If it is close to a constant then $dS_p=0$ to a first approximation. One may note that high n is used because energy levels become very close and dE then makes sense.

As a result, we suggest that there is a possibility of applying thermodynamics to the entropy of a single crest and considering the corresponding energy per crest and using these in thermodynamical equations.

Harmonic Oscillator

The quantum oscillator has energies of $E_n = \hbar \omega (n+.5)$ approx= $c_1 n$ for large n . As a crude approximation we consider the spatial $W^*(x)W(x)$ crests to be more or less the same, e.g. a set of rectangles (even though an envelope through them is of the height $C / v(x)$ where $v(x) = \sqrt{2m(E_n - .5kx^2)}$). Then crudely speaking there is:

$C_1 n/n$ energy per crest if there are n crests in $W_n(x)$. We assume an extra crest appears with each increase in n . Thus $dE_n = 0$ ((4))

The entropy for each crest differs from the infinite well case as the rough length of the system i.e. the length between classical turning points goes as:

$E_n = .5 k x^2$ so x is proportional to \sqrt{n} ((5))

Then: $CC n \sqrt{n}/n = 1$ where C is the wavelength normalization constant. (Here we crudely assume each crest has the same area and that each crest is like a rectangle. The base is \sqrt{n}/n). C is the normalization constant of the wavefunction and CC is proportional to $1/\sqrt{n}$. Then spatial entropy for a single crest (e.g. rectangle) is:

$\sqrt{n}/n \ln(\sqrt{n}/n)$ where the \sqrt{n}/n is the base length, $1/\sqrt{n}$ is proportional to CC or:

S_x for a crest = $1/n (-.5) \ln(n)$ ((6))

Then dS_x for a crest = $C \cdot .5/n^2 dn \ln(n) - .5/n^2 dn$ ((7)) For n very large, $dS_x = C \ln(n)/n^2 dn$.

If one considers T as proportional to E for an oscillator then $T dS_x = \ln(n)/n$ which tends to 0 as n becomes large. This matches ((4)).

(Note: if one considers the ground state $P(x)$ of an oscillator i.e. $C_3 \exp(-\sqrt{k/m} x)$ then this is equivalent to $C_3 \exp(-.5kx / .5 \sqrt{k/m})$ but $E_0 = .5 \sqrt{k/m}$.)

We admit that the above arguments are very hand-wavy, that T is taken to be proportional to E in an ad hoc manner and that only two simple examples have been considered. Nevertheless, we argue that each crest within $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ does resemble a probability distribution and should have its own entropy. In other words there seems to be a localized entropy for each crest which is linked to energy of the crest. “ n ” the energy level may correspond to the number of crests present. Thus it seems that a formalism at the crest level should apply in quantum bound states and that this may be linked to the first law of thermodynamics. Furthermore this formalism may differ from a thermodynamic formalism applied to the overall S and E_n as seen above.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that a quantum bound state $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ may consist of crests each of which is an unnormalized probability density with 0 probability at the endpoints. For example, the ground state in an infinite well consists of a single well representing the full probability distribution. This exact form appears in higher n states although it is now no longer normalized to 1 as there are other crests.

The overall $P(x)$ is a set of these crest distributions which may have different heights. We argue that each crest is like an unnormalized probability distribution. As a result we speculate that one should be able to define spatial entropy for each. Given that a crest is localized to a small region for high n , S_p over all p should apply so we only consider spatial crest entropy.

One may estimate S_x for a crest in terms of n as we have done for an infinite well and quantum oscillator, albeit in a crude manner. Furthermore one may consider E_n / n i.e. the energy per crest if an energy level n has n crests. Finally one may examine whether the first law of thermodynamics $dE = TdS_x$ holds for a crest if one has no PdV term. We consider E proportional to T and examine the high n limit where the spacing between energy levels becomes very small relative to the energy. We find that for the infinite well and oscillator $dE=TdS$ may well hold. We note that for an infinite well the overall dE_n goes as $2n$ while S_x is a constant with respect to n and S_p approaches a constant in n for high n . Thus an examination of thermodynamic behaviour at a crest level appears to be very different from the thermodynamics of the whole system.

References

1. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box